

THERMAL CYCLING OF A 3D WOVEN COMPOSITE: *IN SITU* X-RAY MICRO-TOMOGRAPHY STUDY AND STRAIN FIELD MEASUREMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The increasing use of organic composites in aeronautical structures requires robust life prediction numerical tools. Among the loadings to which the aeronautical structures are submitted, thermal variations should be considered. As thermal coefficient between fibres and matrix are highly different, residual stresses below the curing temperature can promote matrix cracking. In a 3D woven composite, fibres/resin arrangement is complex: carbon fibre tow, sometimes twisted, are weaved in different directions. This leads to a heterogeneous fibre volume fraction, resin rich regions and local discontinuities in mechanical properties. Thus, X-ray micro-tomography is usually used to characterize the meso-level microstructure of the material and visualize the damage initiation areas [1, 2]. To understand the local strain mechanisms which lead to damage initiation, we developed an *in situ* thermal cycling heating stage to scan the specimen at different temperatures. A semi-transparent chamber is used to limit heat exchange and humidity, and the stage can cool and heat the specimen between -70°C and 250°C from the bottom face. Different specimens, with different *a priori* ageing or cycling conditions, were tested. They lead to different damage initiation or propagation temperatures depending on the history of the specimen and the nature of the resin. In addition, to better understanding these phenomena, we have developed and implemented a volumetric strain field measurement technique by digital volume correlation (DVC). To avoid disturbance of the material response, we didn't use artificially added patterns. Indeed, DVC relies on the natural contrast of tomographic data that leads to highly heterogeneous error levels depending on the local phase. A systematic procedure, based on the analysis of rigid movements, was used to estimate the uncertainty of the displacement measurement. The analysis of the strain fields during thermal cycling allows to characterize some mechanisms leading to the damage of the composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

The introduction of 3D Textile Organic Matrix Composites (3DOMC) in primary aeronautical structures needs new reliable mechanical behaviour and life prediction models. These models are based on fine experimental characterizations at the representative scale of the material. Recently, static and fatigue behaviour has been studied by experimental [3, 4] or numerical [5, 6] modelling. Among the loadings under which 3DOMC are submitted, cyclic thermal loadings should be considered. Previous studies on model carbon fibre reinforced polymer laminates have shown that thermal effect can induce intra-laminar matrix cracking depending on their orientations [7]. In fact, stress induced by

inhibited strain between resin and fibres can be high enough to initiate matrix cracks. In particular, cyclic loads imply fatigue phenomena that lead to crack multiplication and propagation. Moreover, previous studies (e.g. [8]) on thermal cycling of CFRP under controlled gaseous environment showed that matrix cracking was more important under oxidative environment because of thermo oxidation of the resin at the surface of the composite. The synergetic effect of oxidation at highest temperatures of the thermal cycling and of the maximization of stress at the lowest temperatures, facilitated the initiation and propagation of cracks. Even if we can suppose similar mechanisms in 3DOMC, their complexity and their large number of resin rich regions require to conduct new studies to evaluate the impact of thermal cycling on their cracking properties. Some recent works in the literature deal with this issue [9, 10]. In [9], authors observed matrix cracking by thermal cycling of 3DOMC by *ex situ* X-Ray radiography and *in situ* Acoustic Emission (AE). In particular, AE events appeared only during negative temperatures of the cycles. This scenario confirms that stresses induced by inhibited thermal expansion, maximum at lowest temperatures, are high enough to initiate and propagate cracks in the matrix. However, the complete mechanism of 3DOMC cracking is not well understood, in particular, we should explain why the cracking is delayed during thermal cycling. Indeed, matrix viscous properties, dependent of temperature, can delay the cracking, but is there any other factor?

The 3D morphology and spatial distribution of cracks in 3DOMC need a volume characterization technique like X-Ray Micro-Computed-Tomography (XR μ CT), to study the link between the architecture of the material and the cracks. In [10], authors studied 3DOMC cracking after post curing cooling by XR μ CT. Thanks to that technique, they pointed out the role of the textile architecture on matrix cracks initiation and propagation, in particular in resin rich regions and interfaces between yarns and resin. [9] showed also that the resin type is of primary importance and that a tough resin could delay or slow down the cracking process. As these tests were down under air atmospheric conditions, we could expect that thermo oxidation would influence the cracking.

In this work, we will characterize the cracking process of a 3DOMC by mean of *in situ* XRS μ CT (X-Ray Synchrotron Micro-Computed-Tomography) thermal cycling tests on the ID19 ESRF synchrotron beam line. The live observation of the cracking in relation with the loading will allow to better understanding the scenario of cracking and is complementary of high numbers of *ex situ* thermal cycles down on different resin type specimens and in oxidative or not gaseous environments. In particular, we want to determine the crack initiation temperature and what are the conditions to multiply or propagate some cracks with several cycles. Moreover, the influence of matrix toughness or of a pre-oxidation will be addressed. Finally, we will implement digital volume correlation (DVC) to enrich the analysis of the tests after characterizing the resolution of the measurements.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Description of the specimens and the *in situ* thermal cycling test

The studied material is a 3D textile carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composite obtained by RTM process. To optimize the resolution, the specimens were machined in a cylindrical shape of 10mm diameter taken from the whole thickness of the composite plates furnished by SNECMA (see Figure 1a). To evaluate the influence of the resin type on matrix cracking, two kinds of specimens with different epoxy resins were studied. The first one is a relatively tough resin, called epoxy 1, and the second one is a more brittle epoxy resin, called epoxy 2. Furthermore, to study the effect of the gaseous environment on a possible embrittlement by thermo-oxidation, some specimens were previously aged in oxidative environment at 120°C, whereas some other ones were pre-cycled thermally between -50°C and 120°C.

Figure 1. (a) Composite specimen. (b) *In situ* thermal cycling stage (-70°C/250°C) for XRSμCT

The *in situ* thermal cycling stage (see Figure 1b) was built in collaboration with Hugo Vitoux from ESRF sample environment team. It is a modification of an existing sample stage for microscopy (Linkam HFS600). In this stage, the heating and cooling of the specimen is done by conduction between the specimen and a sample holder thermally controlled. We have adapted an extension of this sample holder to be able to scan the specimen in rotation for tomography purpose. The cooling is ensured by nitrogen circulation inside the stage and heating by an electric resistance. Finally, a PEEK vacuum enclosure is placed around the specimen to limit the thermal exchanges and avoid frost formation onto the specimen. The temperature is measured by a thermocouple placed near the sample holder and a second one is placed on top of the specimen, through the top of the PEEK enclosure. Before each scan, the temperature is stabilized, however a gradient subsists in the specimen. This gradient was characterized with a thermocouple during an *ex situ* calibration test, after drilling the specimen from top to bottom (see Figure 2) for different cooling conditions. The results reported in Figure 2 show that even if the base of the specimen achieves the desired temperature, the difference with the top of the specimen can reach 40°C.

Figure 2. Temperature gradient in the specimen for two different desired temperatures (-25°C in red, -50°C in blue). Principle of the temperature gradient measurement by a thermocouple in a drilled hole from top to bottom of the specimen.

2.2 XR Synchrotron micro-computed Tomography

XRS μ CT scans were achieved on the ID19 ESRF beam line. This beam line offers several facilities to achieve *in situ* experiments and different kind of imaging modes that can be chosen to optimize the quality of the images depending on the material, the resolution and the application. In our case, the different parameters were optimized to improve the resolution of DVC strain measurements. It should be noted that, unlike other studies (for ex. [5]), we didn't introduced any artificial pattern in the samples to avoid any influence on their behaviour. Thus, the tracking pattern was the natural texture of the material.

- First of all, the voxel size, that defines the spatial resolution of the imaging technique, was limited by the size of the specimen, but was fine enough to reveal the texture of the fibres in the yarn and to visualize the cracks. In our case, depending on the available cameras, we chose a 6.5 μ m pixel size camera.

- Then, due to the low atomic number and poor contrast between carbon fibres and epoxy resin, we decided to use a phase contrast technique with a single distance reconstruction approach, as proposed by Paganin [12]. Indeed, thanks to the high coherence of the beam, it is possible to increase phase contrast as the distance between the specimen and the detector increase (see Figure 3).

- Finally, thanks to the high brilliance of the beam, it is possible to control the energetic spectrum of the beam. In particular, we have used the "pink beam" mode that corresponds to a thin energetic band. This mode leads to high flux, decreasing acquisition time, while avoiding most of polychromatic artefacts.

Figure 3 Representation of a XR synchrotron micro-tomograph with different distance between the sample and the detector to obtain phase contrast (credit R. Boistel)

2.3 Choice of the acquisition and the reconstruction parameters

In view of the mean absorption coefficient of the composite and the capacity of the beam line, two different mean energies were tested: 19keV and 35keV. The more the energy, the less the material absorbs, but phase contrast is also affected. Moreover, as the phase contrast depends on the distance between the specimen and the detector, we tested three distances: 300, 700 and 1000 mm. After several iterations, comparing the contrast and the correlation coefficient, we chose the following combination: energy 35keV, specimen/detector distance 300mm.

When X-rays pass through an object, the material can be described by its refraction index $\tilde{n} = 1 - \delta + i\beta$, where δ control the phase shift and β the absorption of the XR. To reconstruct the data with the Paganin algorithm [12], it is necessary to determine the ratio between δ and β . For Carbon material at 30keV energy, this ratio is equal to about 3000. However, due to the different approximations down on the material and the beam, the optimal value of this parameter should be determined. In particular, as this algorithm tend to smooth the data, to the detriment of spatial resolution, an overestimation of this parameter would erase the texture in the yarns (see Figure 4). Thus, we tested different parameters for the δ/β ratio and evaluate its influence on displacement resolution. The measured displacement errors (standard deviation of the displacement) are reported in Figure 5 for a displacement of 2 μ m in the z direction. We observe that the errors decrease for low values of δ/β , but increase for values lower to 150. Thus, we made a compromise by choosing $\delta/\beta=500$.

Figure 4: Influence of δ/β ratio on reconstruction (from l to r : $\delta/\beta = 300, 1500, 5000$)

Figure 5: Estimation of the displacement error in function of δ/β .

2.4 Digital Volume Correlation

Kinematic field measurements were performed with the CorrelVol software built at P' Institute [13-16] on the principle of local correlation. It consists to match two volumes of a specimen at two different mechanical states to determine the displacement field (see Figure 6). A grid of measurement points is defined at the initial state. For each point, a centred cubic sub-volume is considered and the correlation algorithm looks for the matching sub-volume in the deformed state by maximizing the similarity of the voxel grey level distribution. Each sub-volume is authorized to be deformed homogeneously and a linear interpolation of the grey level is used to reach sub-voxel displacements. The position difference is used to compute the displacement. From the displacement field obtained on each point of the grid, a Green-Lagrange strain field is computed by finite differences [14].

Figure 6 : Principle of DVC.

2.5 Assessment of displacement/strain resolution

To analyse quantitatively strain fields measured by DVC, it is necessary to evaluate the measurement resolution. This last one depends, among others, to signal to noise ratio in the images, and on the artefacts due to image acquisition and reconstruction process. Acquisition and reconstruction parameters were optimised in order to minimize strain measurement resolution (see previous paragraph). Moreover, parameters chosen during correlation process are decisive. According to [17], different types of errors exist. They are for example driven by the relevance between the local mechanical transformation considered and the real one, or by the subsets size, or the grey levels interpolation functions. In this work, in view of the low level of strains, we concentrate on the error linked to the signal to noise ratio. The estimation of the error was thus only made thanks to rigid body motions (i.e. without any deformation) [18]. These displacements were imposed with the translation stages of the tomograph, in the same condition as the *in situ* testing (i.e. with the PEEK cover). The amplitude of the displacements was chosen as a fraction (1/7) of a voxel to characterize the subvoxel resolution. The evolution of the standard deviation and the mean deviation in function of the imposed displacement is reported in Figure 7. The systematic error is equal to $1\mu\text{m}$ that is a reasonable value given the local image texture used for DVC. The random error is higher due to large areas of resin in which grey level gradients are lower. An estimation of this error can be made by computing the standard deviation [14] of all the displacements. It is then about $1.5\mu\text{m}$, that leads to a strain uncertainty of about 0.25% for a gage length of 80 voxels.

Figure 7 : Estimation of the displacement error in function of a subvoxel displacement varying from 0 to $7\mu\text{m}$ (about 1 voxel). The curves represent the mean deviation (systematic error) and the error bars represent the standard deviation (random error).

3 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Matrix cracking analysis

Several thermal cycles were imposed on different specimens during which some μCT scans were realised: at the initial state, and at different time, after a plateau to stabilize the temperature.

A typical thermal loading is given in Figure 8 for which a scan was realised for each temperature plateau. For each scan, the eventual matrix cracks initiation or propagation were controlled visually.

Figure 8 : Typical temperature curves measured by thermocouples on the top (blue) and bottom (orange) of the specimen during *in situ* thermal cycling tests.

As test campaigns on synchrotron beam line are time limited, only few thermal cycles were realised. It is therefore impossible to reproduce the same conditions of hundreds of thermal cycles. The loading rather corresponds to a varying thermal loading on few cycles. As we don't know exactly the thermal history of the material we decided to heat the specimens above the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the resin for few minutes. We supposed that this state is stress free and will be our reference state for stress/strain studies. To evaluate the impact of this initial heating on the cracking process two different tests were realised on specimens made with epoxy 2 (more brittle). The first specimen was cooled directly from ambient temperature to -50°C and the second one was firstly heated slightly above the T_g of the resin for few minutes and then cooled until -50°C . Figure 9 represents two slices of both specimens close to the bottom surface on which we observe no crack for the first one whereas we observe several ones for the second. This experiment illustrates the role of the resin viscosity in the thermal cycling cracking process. In the specimen at room temperature, the resin had time to relax before the cooling at -50°C , whereas the time elapsed between the plateau at T_g and the scan at -50°C for the second one was not enough to relax all the stresses. Therefore, the stresses at -50°C were higher in the second case and promote cracks.

Figure 9: Influence of thermal loading path on cold cracking for the brittle epoxy 2 composite. (a): cooling from ambient temperature. (b) cooling after an initial plateau of 10 min around T_g .

To test the influence of the resin type, we applied the same thermal cycles on 2 composite specimens with exactly the same architecture but with different matrix epoxies. After heating the specimens at T_g for several minutes, we realised different scans during cooling:

- For epoxy 2 composite, we observed some cracks initiating since -25°C , then new ones at -50°C , and also at -75°C . Moreover, as the cracks opened during cooling, and then closed during heating, more cracks were created during repeated cycles between 120°C and -50°C . This result suggests that an accumulative phenomenon or a stress redistribution occurred during repeated cycles.

- For epoxy 1 composite, we observed no cracks during thermal cycling. This result illustrates the fundamental importance of the resin toughness in cracking process by thermal cycling.

Regarding the influence of the environment on cracking process during thermal cycling, previous studies on 2D or 3D OMC [8, 19] showed that oxidizing environments can promote and accelerate cracking. This phenomenon was observed after hundreds of thermal cycles, because the time of exposition at high temperature is sufficient to oxidise significantly the material. During *in situ* tests, it is not possible to reach a long time of exposition, thus some samples were “pre-oxidised” before the campaign during isothermal ageing at 120°C during 200h under 3bars of oxygen. During *in situ* testing, the aged epoxy 1 composite specimen was cracked since -25°C scan and again at -75°C scan whereas there was no crack for virgin specimens at the same temperatures. Moreover, the crack lengths to the bulk of the specimen are always below the depth of the oxidised layer. The pre-oxidation of the resin embrittled the surface of the composite and promoted matrix cracking after only the first cycle.

3.2 Strain field measurements by DVC

Among all the tests conducted during this campaign, only some ones could be analysed by DVC. Indeed DVC is highly sensitive to artefacts, in particular those which change suddenly the grey levels as ring, metal or diffraction artefacts. Results presented here concern a composite specimen scanned between $+25^{\circ}\text{C}$ and -50°C . A temperature amplitude higher than 75°C would have been easier to analyse but some problems occurred during the acquisition of the initial scan around T_g temperature. The global analysis of the strain field measurements indicates that shear and transverse horizontal components were weak and below the estimated strain resolution ($<0.25\%$), whereas the vertical strain component was higher. The Figure 10 shows some slices of the vertical component of the strain field tensor superimposed with corresponding slices of the microstructure. We observe a strong matching between the microstructure and the strain field: strain in warp yarns are very low (or below the resolution), whereas they can reach -0.3 to -0.4% in weft yarns that may be influenced by subsets spanning on interfaces. Strain at yarn interfaces and in resin rich regions can even attain -1% . But, we also found some higher erratic values in resin rich regions, which should be due to a lack of contrast in large resin area (blue and purple points in Figure 10). These results showed that the main strain mechanism during thermal loading is out of plane heterogeneous expansion obviously due to the large number of fibres oriented horizontally.

Figure 10: Strain field vertical component ϵ_{zz} (longitudinal axis of the cylinder = out of plane textile direction) between 25°C and -50°C scans. Gauge length is about 80 voxels (520 μ m).

Considering the low level of strain and the high level of noise, it is interesting to compute mean level per phase (each yarn individually and the resin) to better reveal the strain contrasts. Figure 11 shows a slice of the vertical strain component averaged per phase. We retrieve the same previous tendencies that strain in weft yarn are slightly higher than in warp yarns. Results in resin rich regions are more scattered.

Figure 11: (a) segmentation of the material: colors indicating the phase (green: weft, blue/purple: warp, red: resin). (b) Vertical cut of strain field averaged per phase.

CONCLUSION

During this study, we developed an XRS μ CT *in situ* thermal cycling test on 3D textile OMC to better understand and observe the cracking mechanism during thermal loading. The results confirmed the initiation and multiplication of cracks at low temperatures. The cracking process depends on the temperature history loading path of the specimen, and on the type of resin, in particular its toughness.

A pre-oxidation during thermal ageing of the specimen embrittles the composite and promotes cracking. Results obtained by DVC are a partial success because of low contrast, in particular in resin rich regions. However, some tendencies on strain heterogeneities in relation with the microstructure were obtained. New studies are ongoing to improve the image quality for DVC and go farther in understanding of strain mechanisms.

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